

SOCIAL SCIENCES

THE USE OF THE FACEBOOK SOCIAL NETWORK IN THE INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES OF LIBRARY ANALYTICAL UNITS UNDER WARTIME CONDITIONS

Natarov O.

Junior Researcher,

V. I. Vernadskyi National Library of Ukraine,

Kyiv, Ukraine,

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1183-2323>

ABSTRACT

With the onset of the full-scale Russian-Ukrainian war, domestic library institutions began to use social networks more actively to establish communication with their users. The relevance of utilizing these platforms by Ukrainian libraries as a tool for communication and a means of effective interaction with their audiences is due to the fact that, enjoying stable popularity among users, social media have effectively become the main information channel both in Ukraine and abroad.

The use of social networks during wartime is of particular importance in the activities of library information and analytical units, whose role is significantly strengthened under conditions of intensified military and informational confrontation. In particular, library and information centers such as Ukraine's largest library institution – the V. I. Vernadskyi National Library of Ukraine – possess information and analytical resources capable of countering the spread of enemy narratives as well as shaping and disseminating Ukraine's national narrative.

Today, a prime example of the effective use of the Facebook social network as a communication tool between a library and its users is demonstrated by one of the leading domestic library analytical units – the Information and Analytical Support Service for Public Authorities of the V. I. Vernadskyi National Library of Ukraine.

The content of the IASS page at the Facebook social network is shaped by the areas of its activity and its main tasks, and therefore features a subject focus specific to this structural unit. In particular, one of the important applied scientific tasks of the IASS is the study of modern scientific approaches to the preservation of internet-based information by libraries, as well as the preservation of a wide range of socio-political, legal, and economic online content through its consolidated presentation in information-analytical products. Accordingly, one of the key features of the IASS page at the Facebook social network is informing users about the creation of these information-analytical products.

Thus, there are all grounds to draw the following conclusion: today, under wartime conditions, the Information and Analytical Support Service of the V.I. Vernadskyi National Library of Ukraine (IASS of the VNLU) is actively using the Facebook social network as a tool for interacting with its users and as an important channel for disseminating information about its own information-analytical products.

Keywords: libraries, social networks, Facebook, IASS, information and analytical products.

Problem statement

The quarantine period caused by the global COVID-19 pandemic, followed by the full-scale Russian invasion of Ukraine, has brought about significant changes in the activities of Ukrainian library institutions. In particular, libraries of various types across the country have begun to make more active use of social media in order to establish communication and ensure effective interaction with their users.

It should be noted that, under wartime conditions, the use of social media by Ukrainian libraries as a communication channel with their audiences acquires particular importance. In particular, contemporary researchers associate the effectiveness of communication in social media during the full-scale Russian invasion of Ukraine with "...the ability of social media to reveal and consolidate information, influencing the formation of public opinions, views, and sentiments..." [1, p. 23], as well as with the fact that social media have assumed the role of the primary information channel both in Ukraine and abroad [2, p. 108].

The views of scholars are supported by data from sociological surveys. For instance, according to the results of the nationwide sociological survey "Post-war Recovery of Ukraine and Media Consumption", conducted in 2024 by the Ilko Kucheriv Democratic Initiatives Foundation in cooperation with the Centre for Political Sociology, the main sources of daily news for Ukrainian respondents are YouTube (41%), local Telegram channels (39%), national Telegram channels (37%), Facebook (36%), other people (35%), and the "United News" telethon (38%). The most popular social media platforms among respondents are Telegram (62%), Facebook (53.5%), Instagram (31%), and TikTok (30%). At the same time, respondents primarily used social media for communication (67%), browsing news feeds of information resources (38%), and following updates from acquaintances (35%) [3]. In turn, the findings of studies on the Ukrainian media landscape conducted by the civic network OPORA also indicate that during the full-scale Russian-Ukrainian war, social media have maintained stable popularity and remain the most widely used source of news. Thus, in 2022, 53.9% of citizens trusted news from social media; in

2023 – 60%; and in 2024 – 47.3%. The proportion of respondents who used social media to consume news was 76.6% in 2022, 77.9% in 2023, and 73.4% in 2024 [4].

Analysis of recent research and publications

The issue of libraries' use of social media during the Russian-Ukrainian war has attracted the attention of many Ukrainian scholars. In particular, Yu. Polovynchak and A. Berehelskyi devoted their study to identifying optimal strategies for the formation of library collections of visual content, using as an example visual material of various origins created for dissemination on social media during the 2022 military invasion. The authors substantiated the feasibility of such archiving in view of the influential role of communication in social media [1]. S. Ivanenko, addressing in her work the problem of interaction between libraries and users in times of social crises, examined the use of the social network Facebook as an effective tool for social interaction and the promotion of library media products [5]. Byrkovych and Ya. Morozova, in their article, analyzed the representation of Ukrainian libraries on social media platforms such as Instagram, TikTok, and YouTube. The authors emphasized the leading role of social media in informing users, promoting resources and services, and facilitating communication in wartime conditions [6]. N. Zubko and N. Prokopenko, in their study, revealed the specific features of the communication activities of the Vasyl Stefanyk Lviv National Scientific Library of Ukraine via the social network Facebook [7].

In turn, the specific features of the information and communication activities of library institutions under conditions of military and information confrontation have been examined by such scholars as O. Aulin [8], T. Byrkovych and I. Vilchynska [9], O. Zhelai [10], O. Natarov [11], M. Sakharova and Ya. Khimich [12]. In particular, O. Aulin, in his study, analyzed the specifics of library and information activities during a military conflict in the context of intensified information warfare. The author emphasized that during this period, destructive external influences on the information space of Ukraine pose a significant threat. The researcher demonstrated that “domestic library institutions can play a positive role in countering fake Russian narratives, as well as in shaping and disseminating a national narrative” [8, p. 43]. T. Byrkovych and I. Vilchynska comprehensively investigated the essence of the information and communication activities of libraries in the context of Russia's war against Ukraine and identified the role of communication strategies in implementing their core functions. The researchers concluded that “libraries in the information and communication space under wartime conditions have undergone a transformation from a traditional environment into a social platform capable of resisting the enemy's informational, cultural, and psychological influences” [9, p. 47]. O. Zhelai, in her article, examined the scientific, methodological, and practical aspects of organizing library and information services, in particular library and analytical services, in accordance with the information needs of society in wartime. She also analyzed the role of the scientific library within the system of countering Russian information aggression. The author reviewed

and generalized the experience of the Information and Analytical Support Service of Public Authorities of the V.I. Vernadskyi National Library of Ukraine (hereinafter – IAS VNLU) in providing information and analytical support to government bodies and meeting societal information needs during the wartime period, and identified effective methodological approaches to the production of information-based scientific and intellectual library products [10]. Using the example of the IAS VNLU's activities in providing users with materials on socially significant topics, O. Natarov highlighted the role of libraries as information and communication institutions under the legal regime of martial law in Ukraine [11].

At the same time, the significant role of libraries, which during the Russian-Ukrainian war have become distinctive information and communication, multifunctional social platforms operating on the information front [9, p. 45], as well as the role of social media as a communication tool and a means of effective interaction between libraries and their audiences, underscores the relevance of studying the use of social media by library institutions under conditions of military and information confrontation.

It should be noted that the relevance of this research area was previously outlined by the author during the International Scientific Conference “Library. Science. Communication. Integration into the International Library Space” (Kyiv city, October 2024). The present article is an expanded and more in-depth version of the theses presented at the aforementioned conference.

Thus, **the aim of the article** is to generalize the experience of the IAS VNLU in using the social network Facebook as a communication channel with its audience under wartime conditions.

Presentation of the main research material

Today, social media function as a tool for integrating library institutions into the global information space, an important network channel for disseminating information, and a means of effective interaction between libraries and their audiences. We agree with the view of L. Poperechna, who considers social media as a specific communication system “that opens up broad opportunities for promoting library resources and services, exerting a managed influence on the formation of public opinion, establishing active communication and effective interaction with users (on their own territory), in order to strengthen the competitive position of the library institution and to position it in society primarily as an important socially oriented institution” [13].

As noted above, the use of social media by Ukrainian library institutions has gained particular importance in the context of the full-scale Russian-Ukrainian war.

Thus, T. Byrkovych and Ya. Morozova, examining the peculiarities of using social media for the promotion of library resources, argue that “under wartime conditions, the library as a social institution is one of the subsystems of the information and communication system, whose activities are characterized by a diversity of directions and the use of a wide range of forms of work to meet the needs of numerous users. War transforms library institutions, which are forced to

adapt to new requirements and become centers in communication processes between the reader and information" [6, p. 56]. The authors regard social media as "a powerful tool for libraries that enables them to communicate with users, promote their services, explore audience interests, optimize their activities, and maintain feedback with users" [6, p. 57].

In their study on the information and communication activities of libraries in Ukraine under wartime conditions, T. Byrkovych and I. Vilchynska consider social media as an important factor in ensuring the effective and multifaceted information and communication activities of libraries. "Social media represent a symbiosis of social and technical reality, through which all types of social communication are carried out: mass, group, and interpersonal, across all technological and library resources – audio-visual, oral, and verbal – which has a decisive impact on the development of Ukrainian society" [9, p. 45].

For her part, S. Ivanenko, examining the issue of interaction between libraries and users in times of social crises, using the example of Facebook in user services at the library of a research institution of the National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine, concludes that "the use of social media in the work of a scientific library contributes to the formation of a positive image of the library on the global Internet, enables maintaining contact with users under difficult conditions, and enhances interaction with the target audience in a convenient and modern format" [5, p. 82].

It should be emphasized that, under conditions of intensified military and information confrontation during the Russian-Ukrainian war, the role of library and analytical services for users has significantly increased, as has the role of library information and analytical units. As O. Zhelai notes, "contemporary challenges, in particular the Russian-Ukrainian war and hostile information campaigns, encourage domestic libraries to adapt their activities in accordance with changing user demands and highlight the importance of information and scientific-analytical library support across all spheres of social relations: from promoting state policy and national interests in strategic communications to addressing issues in the everyday lives of citizens" [10, p. 228]. "In the context of modern military conflicts, the role of the information component is constantly increasing," writes O. Aulin. "The opposing sides must deliver powerful informational impacts on the adversary's information space while simultaneously protecting their own. Within the framework of information warfare, an important role is played by the creation of one's own and the refutation of hostile information narratives. In this context, the role of library and information centers such as the VNLU, which possess information and analytical resources capable of counteracting the dissemination of the adversary's narratives, as well as shaping and promoting Ukraine's national narrative, is significantly enhanced" [8, p. 43].

One of the leading domestic library information and analytical units operating within the structure of the largest library institution in Ukraine – the V.I. Vernadskyi National Library of Ukraine – is the Information and Analytical Support Service of Public Authorities (IAS, the Service).

It is worth noting that during the period of martial law, the scientific and practical activities of the Service in providing information and analytical support to users consist of ensuring professional monitoring of online media through the use of a wide range of Internet tools and information and communication technologies for the accumulation and systematization of electronic resources on specific topics; analyzing electronic information resources and producing expert conclusions based on the study of the functioning of the media sphere, as well as examining the impact of negative factors on the Ukrainian information space and the dynamics of their manifestation in the life of individual communities and society, especially during wartime; producing information and analytical outputs across a wide range of topics and in optimal formats in accordance with societal information demands, specific issues, or client requirements; ensuring the prompt transfer of information and analytical products to clients; and enriching the website of the Centre for Social Communications Research of the VNLU with information products [10, pp. 241-242].

The Service maintains its own communication channel with users on the social network Facebook – the page entitled "IAS 'Information and Analytical Support Service of Public Authorities'" (<https://www.facebook.com/siazua>). As of March 2026, the audience of this resource comprised 624 followers.

It should be noted that the content of the page is determined by the Service's areas of activity and its core tasks and, accordingly, reflects the thematic specificity of this structural unit. In particular, an important scientific and applied task of the IAS today is the study of contemporary scientific approaches to the preservation of information from the Internet environment by libraries and the safeguarding of a wide range of online information of socio-political, legal, and economic orientation through its consolidated presentation in information and analytical products. IAS publications are intended for scholars, political scientists, sociologists, lawyers, journalists, and public organizations engaged in the study and analysis of issues related to the functioning of public authorities in Ukraine, problems of domestic and foreign policy, as well as for employees of relevant public services, government bodies at all levels, and local self-government authorities.

It should be noted that informing users about the information and analytical products created by the Service is one of the distinctive features of the content of the IAS Facebook page.

As an example of using the social network Facebook to promote its own information and analytical products, one may cite the publication on the page of announcements for the edition "Ways of Development of Ukrainian Science: Public Discourse" – an information and analytical bulletin based on prompt information, which highlights issues related to increasing the efficiency of scientific activity, the progress of reforms in Ukrainian science, its contribution to social development and the strengthening of national defense capability, and provides information on international scientific cooperation, achievements of domestic science, and experience in the development of scientific

research abroad. Thus, from the beginning of the full-scale Russian invasion of Ukraine to the present (as of March 2026), 137 posts containing multimedia content have been published on the aforementioned Facebook page.

The analysis of the IAS Facebook page, aimed at identifying the content of its materials, made it possible to distinguish several thematic blocks that, under wartime conditions, are reflected on this social media platform:

• ***the role of science during wartime, in particular the contributions of Ukrainian scholars aimed at bringing victory closer, strengthening defense capacity, and rebuilding and developing Ukraine***, for example:

- Science for strengthening the defense capability and national security of Ukraine;
- The Ministry of Defense launches an Innovation Development Accelerator;
- Memorandum of cooperation between the State Special Transport Service and the Institute of History of Ukraine;
- The “Historiographical Front” of the Russian-Ukrainian war;
- Archaeology of Ukraine during wartime: Problems and prospects;
- Culture as an integral humanitarian component in the de-occupation of Crimea;
- Science during wartime;
- Post-war development and reform of Ukrainian science: views of scholars and analysts.

• ***international scientific cooperation, primarily international initiatives aimed at supporting Ukrainian scholars***:

- Information on current calls under the Horizon Europe Program;
- Recommendations for preparing project proposals under the Horizon Europe Program;
- Participation of Ukrainian stakeholders in projects within the Horizon Europe Program;
- Ukraine’s participation in Horizon Europe programs 2026-2027;
- The European Commission increases support for displaced Ukrainian researchers;
- The Rome Declaration of Intent in the field of science, research, and innovation in Ukraine;
- Second meeting of the Ukraine-EU / Euratom Committee on Research and Innovation;
- Grant opportunities from NATO for Ukrainian scholars;
- Ukraine strengthens scientific cooperation with CERN;
- Fulbright Research and Development Program 2025-2026;
- DAAD Scholarship Program.

• ***implementation of state policy in the field of science and innovation***:

- Approval of the Roadmap for the use of science, technology, and innovation to achieve the Sustainable Development Goals;
- The Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine adopted a resolution on the training and certification of academic and research staff;

- Extraordinary certification of research institutions and higher education institutions;
- A new model for financing the scientific sector;
- Approval of the procedure for the distribution of basic funding for research institutions based on the results of the state certification in 2025;
- A new state system of individual support for researchers;
- The Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine developed a new methodology for evaluating the effectiveness of scientific and technical activities of research institutions and higher education institutions;
- The Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine introduces a unified simplified reporting system for research projects across all areas of governance;
- The Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine revises approaches to the formation of the List of professional scientific journals;
- New rules for the formation of the List of professional scientific journals of Ukraine;
- The Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine initiates the creation of a National Researcher System;
- The volumes of state-funded places for doctoral (PhD) training have been announced;
- Admission rules for doctoral (PhD) studies in 2024.

• ***scientific communication as an integral component of research and innovation***:

- Podcasts as an effective tool for promoting scientific research;
- Access to sources of scientific information;
- EU Funding & Me: a mobile application that facilitates access to the EU funding portal;
- Science Day in Ukraine;
- Fundamentals of working with Google Scholar;
- Publishing articles in journals of Bentham Science Publisher;
- Remote access to resources of the Research4Life platform;
- Checklist for scientific journals;
- Survey for researchers, lecturers, and PhD students in Ukraine.

• ***scientific articles and analytical materials produced by IAS researchers***:

- Foreign investment in Ukraine as a factor of post-war economic recovery;
- War and Ukraine’s strategic mineral resources;
- Losses of Ukraine’s agricultural sector as a result of the war: assessments and forecasts;
- Water resources of Ukraine during wartime: key challenges and prospects for their resolution;
- The destruction of the Kakhovka Hydropower Plant: global response, consequences of the disaster, and prospects for reconstruction;
- Environmental rehabilitation of land as a component of overcoming the consequences of the Russian-Ukrainian war;
- The war with Russia: losses and risks for Ukraine’s cultural heritage;

– Psychological adaptation of Ukrainian Armed Forces servicemen to civilian life: scientific and organizational aspects.

It is also worth noting that the posts published on the IAS Facebook page are accompanied by hyperlinks to issues of the information and analytical bulletin “Ways of Development of Ukrainian Science: Public Discourse” on the website of the Centre for Social Communications Research (<https://nbuviap.gov.ua/>), an information platform that currently represents the information-analytical and scientific activities of the analytical units of the VNLU (the Information and Analytical Support Service of Public Authorities, the National Law Library, and the Presidential Library of Ukraine). Thus, even under wartime conditions, and especially during the period of remote operation of the library at the beginning of the full-scale invasion, users (primarily scholars, media representatives, public organizations, employees of relevant public services, government bodies at all levels, and local self-government authorities, as noted above) had access to information and analytical publications and, consequently, to prompt information across a wide thematic range.

Conclusions

With the onset of the full-scale Russian-Ukrainian war, domestic library institutions have intensified their use of social media to establish communication with their users. The increased use of social media by libraries as a communication tool and a means of interaction with their audiences is driven by their sustained popularity among users, as social media have effectively assumed the role of the primary information channel both in Ukraine and abroad.

The use of social media during wartime acquires particular significance in the activities of library information and analytical units, whose role is considerably strengthened under conditions of intensified military and information confrontation.

Under the conditions of the ongoing war, an example of effective use of the social network Facebook as a communication tool between a library and its users is demonstrated by one of the leading domestic library analytical units – the IAS VNLU.

The content of the IAS Facebook page is determined by the Service’s areas of activity and its core tasks and, accordingly, reflects the thematic specificity of this structural unit. An important scientific and applied task of the IAS is the study of contemporary approaches to the preservation of Internet-based information by libraries and the safeguarding of a wide range of online information of socio-political, legal, and economic orientation through its consolidated presentation in information and analytical products. Accordingly, one of the key features of the content of the IAS Facebook page is informing users about the information and analytical publications produced by the Service.

Thus, it can be concluded that, under wartime conditions, the IAS VNLU actively uses the social network Facebook as a tool for interaction with its users and as an important channel for disseminating information about its own information and analytical products.

Further research is planned to focus on studying international experience in the use of social media in

the activities of analytical and research units of leading libraries worldwide.

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